

From 0 to 1: How Objective Entities Become Subjectively Real and the Process of Measurement

By Allan Porter

“If there exist two ways of looking at something then there must also exist at least two somethings”

Objectivity and Subjectivity

In order to understand the process of measurement, a fundamental dichotomy must first be established between objectivity and subjectivity. While subjectively, an entity's properties are reliant on the “context” of what surrounds it at a given time, objectively an entity must always have the same properties regardless of its surroundings. For example, subjectively an entity could appear as “large” or “small” depending on one's distance when observing it. That being said, the entity itself would always still be the same size objectively. This is because its “inherent size” wouldn't actually change objectively depending on the context in which it is placed in but only “seem” to change subjectively in a certain context.

In fact, any concept of “size” at all would be meaningless for an objective entity since objectively it always is only looked at on its own regardless of its surroundings. Again, this is because taking into account its surrounding entities would “contextualize” it and therefore render it subjectively based. Using this logic that an entity always exists only on its own objectively regardless of its surroundings, there would be no way to actually ever judge its “size” since size itself is a relational term that is only “meaningful” when comparing multiple entities. Therefore, if an entity is objective and only looked at on its own, its size could then never be “defined” since there would be no other objects to compare it to and therefore no scale on which its size could ever be measured.

Furthermore, in order to for an object to have a size at all it must be “measurable” by an outside entity. This taking into account of an outside entity would therefore by definition “contextualize” the entity rendering it as no longer objective (since its properties are now dependent on an outside entity and therefore subjective). In this way, the “size” of an objective entity would be meaningless since size is a relational term that requires both measurement and its comparison with other entities.

Moreover, the same could be said for other properties such as velocity and position. After all like size, both velocity and position are only meaningful properties when comparing multiple entities to one another. For example, in terms of velocity, any object on its own has no “dimensional axis” to exist in (since it only exists on its own) and therefore can't have a speed since speed itself requires an entity to have a delta in a dimension. Furthermore, the same can be said of position since position itself is also only significant if there are multiple entities that can be compared in relation to one another across a specific dimension. If an entity however is conceptualized only on its own then it can never have a “position” since it would lack a “dimension” for it to ever be placed in. Therefore relational properties such as size, velocity and position would all be meaningless when describing the “objective” natures of things.

Defining Measurement

Measurement can therefore be described as the process of taking an objective entity that exists only on its own with no relational properties and subsequently placing it inside of a “context” where it could take on a subjective existence with relational properties. Once such an entity is measured, it therefore can be said to have a size, velocity and position since it is now not “only existing on its own” but also “existing among other entities”.

Now considering that all properties generally used to describe an entity are subjectively based, what properties would be objectively based at all? In order to understand what properties can ever be objectively based, there must first be an understanding of what “objectively” can be said to exist in the first place.

What Exists Objectively?

The Infinite Whole

Objectively, there is only a single “everything that exists”. This “total everything that exists” is what fundamentally has to make up the totality of all of physical reality since it needs to constitute everything there is. Such an “everything that exists” can be thought of as a whole border-less single block of *content* that expands forever in every conceivable dimension. This “everything” can be referred to as “infinity” or the infinite whole.

Properties of Infinity

Such a true “everything” by definition needs to be static and as a whole never change. For if it did change it would not truly be “everything” since it could eventually change into “something else”. Since “something else” would need to be included in “everything”, the true everything would therefore need to be unchangeable in that it includes all “something else’s” and possible states of itself.

Furthermore, true everything should only ever exist as one separated whole without components. This is because the only way that anything ever has “parts” or “separations” within it is if there is a contextualization to that anything that essentially “splits” it into parts in order to make sense of it. The notion of the separation of an “anything” into its components therefore does not exist if there is no outside entity to contextualize said “anything” and separate its parts through analysis. Since true “everything” would need to include all possible “observers” and “contextualizers”, a true everything cannot be separated since there would be no outside entity to separate it. After all, nothing can essentially “separate” itself into components. One can only ever separate “other things” that are not oneself into components. This is because what one essentially is, can never be viewed from their perspective since it IS their perspective. For example, an eye can never see itself. It can see a reflection of the “light” that hits it and its information thereby portrayed onto a mirror, but this light wouldn’t actually “be” the eye but rather the “subjective information” of the eye from the context of the mirror. Furthermore, it can only ever “analyze” such second hand information about itself with the inclusion of an outside entity (a mirror) to first observe it

and then “show” the eye its subjective observation. The reason the eye can’t ever observe its “actual self” is obviously because it IS the eye. Since the eye can never “see” itself, it can also never analyze itself, break itself down into components or separate itself any way.

In this way separation of the “eye” requires the observation of the “eye” and since the eye can’t observe itself there needs to be something else that observes it in order for the eye to ever be considered “separated” in any way. Therefore, it is fair to say that since separation requires observation and since nothing can observe itself, then presumably the “everything” that exists can’t either observe itself which means it also can’t separate itself and if it doesn’t separate itself there can be no objective separations within it. Even if it is argued that this “everything” is capable of observation, such observation would require an external “mirror” for it to ever observe and then separate itself. Obviously an external mirror could not exist as if it did the “everything” would not really be “everything” since it wouldn’t include the external mirror. For this reason such an everything must always lack any separations and can only be referred to as the “infinite whole” not the infinite with parts.

Information-less Os

However, because separable individual entities do exist, infinity must actually be “separable” (or else individual things wouldn’t exist). Perhaps while it is true that infinity as a whole cannot be itself “separated”, it still must nevertheless objectively consist of “potential indivisible components”. This is because any “thing” is generally only separated when a subject can take the “whole” thing and conceptually conceive of its different parts in a subjective way. However, any “whole” thing must itself be composed of “fundamental indivisible components” that themselves exist regardless of an observers conceptions of said “thing”. Therefore, while it is true that any separation of a “thing” is based on its subjective conception by an observer, it is also true that said “thing” must consist of indivisible parts regardless of the “context” in which its part are separated.

Therefore, objectively there needs to exist at least “indivisible bits” that are themselves objective. Again this is because any “thing” must always itself contain fundamental indivisible parts. Therefore, while the actual nature of what constitutes a “part” is subjective, there is still essentially a “smallest most indivisible” component of every potential “thing” that needs to objectively exist. This “indivisible” component would exist as the same thing regardless of subject purely because it by definition can’t be separated and always must exist as only one separate-less whole.

Furthermore, these “indivisible fundamental bits” must themselves not have any “information” associated with them. This is because since they are indivisible they can only contain one objective property - that of existence. Any other property given to them would essentially render them as having “2 properties” which itself would mean that they would need to be divisible and different from one another based on potential differences in this second property. For example if an indivisible bit had a property of chirality (right vs. left handedness), then indivisible bits themselves could be categorized as being either right or left handed and therefore have discoverable information associated with them. However, if they are truly indivisible there would be nothing within them that actually causes them to have an inherent differential property

of chirality. Therefore since they can't possibly contain any "mechanism" of such a differentiable property, they must only "exist" without any informational aspects.

Furthermore, since they are fundamental they cannot be different from one another in any way and therefore must be "information-less". In this way they can be conceived as "0s" or physical 0's in line with Massimo Melli's conception of "logons". This is because they essentially always will have 0 size and quantity in any conceivable dimension other than a base dimension of existence. Obviously, this lack of "size" in any dimension is because they contain no "information" so are objective. If they had any "finite" size in any dimension that means that their size would need to itself exhibit information and also be "subjectively based". Therefore, these 0's themselves could be thought of as "objective indivisible components". Objectively, there therefore must not only exist "infinity" (the everything that exists) but also the "objective indivisible information-less" components within it.

Now there exists a question of how any amount of "information-less 0s" can actually make up any finite thing in any dimension if they themselves lack an "existence" in every such possible dimension. For since each individual one of these 0s has no information and the whole that they make up does have information, there must then be an "inconceivable" or perhaps infinite number of them in order to make up any "discrete" component. This is because any finite number of size-less entities will still be size-less so only an infinite number of them could actually ever constitute a finite size. This process of how an infinite number of information-less entities can constitute an actual informational entity can be seen through the thought experiment "Zeno's Arrow".

Zeno's Arrow

In Zeno's Arrow, an arrow is fired across a field and its journey throughout is broken up into static photograph like "moments". In each moment the arrow itself never actually moves and always is just static. Yet it is known that the actual arrow must move in order to make it to the other side of the field. This shows that while within each moment the actual arrow exhibits "0" movement, when there is an infinite number of moments, the arrow then can actually move in a "more than the sum of its parts" fashion.

Furthermore, the reason there must be an infinite amount of these "moments" is because the arrows actual journey being broken down into finite smaller and smaller journeys will never actually result in any indivisible journey. Yet there must inherently be a static indivisible journey or *moment* at the heart of each sub-journey the arrow takes across the field. Therefore since there cannot be a finite amount of these "moments" that make up the arrows journey, there must be an infinite amount. Now this jump from an infinite amount of static moments to finite "non-static" journeys alone is impossible using just a collection of static moments. After all how can any amalgamation of 0 movement moments result in a finite movement journey? This jump alone does not objectively happen but rather can only be explained by the presence of subjective "contextualizers" and the process of measurement.

The Process of Measurement

Imagine a 0 dimensional axis. Such an axis only consists of one possible coordinate point with no tangible size or depth. This is because the point itself is just a point and has no conceivable size in any dimension. It exists only on its own objectively with no concept of any other entities since it has no dimension for any other entities to exist in. However now add a dimension and imagine that such a point now has a real length in one dimension. This point becomes a “line” and takes on a certain finite size.

The size of such a “line” can only itself be defined by its measurer since before it is measured it lacks any “conceivable” scale to be measured on. For since any finite sized line can essentially be broken down an infinite number of times before it is just indivisible 0 sized points, this means that objectively it is always the same size - an infinite number of indivisible 0's. This is to say that prior to being measured, any one dimensional line lacks a finite size and can only be described as an amalgamation of an infinite number of 0 dimensional coordinates. However, once the line is “subjectively measured” and placed inside of a subjective context it then exists on a “scale” where it could be measured in comparison to other lines within the context and therefore have a “real relative size”.

This means that only the measurer of the line that “measures” it as a subjectively finite value can provide it with a finite “size”. In this way, the difference between a linear path being 30,000 miles long and 3 nanometers long is actually nothing objectively. Objectively such a line is always just an infinite number of 0 dimensional points long. Again, this is because it lacks any “dimensional existence” of length and therefore only consists of an infinite number of indivisible bits which can eventually be amalgamated as “potentially existing in a dimension of length”.

However, when the measurer measures the line, such a line must take on a “finite measurement” in the world of the measurer which then can be 3 nanometers, 30,000 miles or any other finite value depending on what measurement “fits” in with the scale on which it is placed in the context of the measurer. Note that this doesn't mean that the length of the line changes when measured. Objectively it is always the same size prior to measurement and after measurement - an infinite amount of 0s. Rather only in the subjective world of the measurer can it manifest itself as a finite value when measured.

This idea of finite sizes only being able to exist upon measurement should not be a controversial idea in any right since all measurement is based on human perception and there is never any way to actually prove that one line has “more” points within it than any other line (since all lines can always be broken down into an infinite amount of points).

How 0's takes on information

Now there exists a question of how any amalgamation of infinite zeroes can actually ever take on “real” sizes. After all, if they are information-less 0 dimensional objects how can they ever become informational n dimensional objects? How can n dimensions come into existence from 0?

To understand this, again imagine each information-less 0 as a 0 dimensional point with all possible other 0's juxtaposed onto it. This is because since all 0s are 0 dimensional they must all

exist at the same position. For since they lack any possible information they also lack any concept of differentiable position and therefore must exist all at the same position.

However, when these "0"s are measured by an observer, the observer provides for them a real "context" for them to exist within. This context can be thought of as a "plane" or added dimension for the 0's to now exist within. Suddenly, while before all 0's were confined to the same point because they lacked any real dimensional existence, they now "exist" in the subjective "context" of the observer and therefore take on real dimensional depth in this plane. This "plane" that the 0s now exist in could therefore be thought of as a "first" dimension.

This concept of dimensional expansion can be understood by imagining how a zero dimensional point can be drawn in a first dimension. Just because it seems to only be a singular "point" in 0 dimensions does not mean that it doesn't actually have a depth in a first dimension but rather only means that its' first dimensional depth is not apparent. Once it however can be measured in the first dimension, its first dimensional depth then exists and can be seen since it is now a line. If however, it was then converted back to only having a 0 dimensional existence, it would then again exist only as a 0 sized point. Whether it exists in 0 or 1 dimensions, the actual entity itself never changes, it rather only seems to change based on the dimensional context in which it is placed in.

Now that it is understood how 0 dimensional entities are able to have real depth in a "first" dimension it can also be understood how these 0s no longer need to be confined to only one point but can now be "spread out" across a first dimension. However, how is it decided how much depth these 0s have and how spread out they are? Should they have an infinite amount of depth in the first dimension because there is an infinite amount of them? However, if they are still each of 0 size inherently how can it make sense that any number of 0s could be anything other than 0?

The answer is that the 0 dimensional point that contained an infinite number of 0s can take on any "finite size" in the dimension of the measurer. For once they are placed in the "subjective plane of existence" of the measurer upon measurement they now have another dimension to exist in which allows them to together take on real informational properties such as position and length. While prior to being "measured" these 0's could not have any size since they were 0 dimensional, they are now 1 dimensional and could therefore take on real informational properties that come along with existing as a 1 dimensional entity (or in this case a line). In 1 dimension, a position of a line can also be defined based on where the line exists within the dimension relative to other lines.

Note that this "line" must still consist of the original infinite 0s but now actually has a "real dimensional existence" inside the context of the measurer which allows it to take on informational properties such as size and position. These properties however are completely subjective and depend only on how a measurer measures them.

Furthermore, these infinite 0's are still objectively 0 dimensional information-less entities all existing on the same point. However, to an observer, an infinite amount of 0's are measured as a "discrete informational dimensional entity" that will fit in with the existing information of the

observers world. This means that the measurer is essentially intaking a conceptual “holographic copy” of the infinite 0s and defining them as being of finite informational properties based on the rest of the information that they are maintaining within their context. This process of measuring these objective 0's and providing them existence in the first dimension of context allows the 0s to take on finite sizes that can then be compared to other entities that exist within the measurers existing context.

The higher dimensional existence of these infinite 0s when in a subjective context is what allows them essentially to take on a “more than the sum of their parts” subjective existence as a line that is reality is still objectively just an infinite number of 0s.

Informational Worlds

To explain the specific finite informational properties that the infinite 0s take on, understand that when they are measured by an observer, the observer is “placing them” into the observers “informational world”. Such an observers “informational world” consists of all of the information that they must maintain in order to have cohesive causal experiences. For example, if an observer hears a chirp there must be an observable bird. This is because the informational phenomenon that is an audial “chirp” requires a cause for said chirp. This cause must then be informationally fitting with the chirp itself.

Perhaps, this means that there is no “linear causality” but rather only “information” that needs to fit cohesively in the “context” of an observer in order to maintain a sense of causality. This strive for causality and maintaining cohesive information is what essentially defines the subjective finite sizes of things. For example in the case of size, if one picks up a stone without looking and feels that it fits nicely in their hand, then when they open their hand to look at the stone it must be measured to be a size that is small enough to fit in a hand. This is because “information” must make sense with other “information” when they exist in a shared context.

Up until now every measurement of any finite entity has been declared as completely subjective. However if multiple observers can measure the same entity as having the same properties wouldn't that mean said properties are objective and not subjective? After all, wouldn't agreed upon information by multiple observers render the information as objectively true? If 2 people both measure a stone as the same size, wouldn't the stone objectively be said size?

The answer is that what constitutes a subjective informational context is perhaps not confined to only one observer, but rather a series of observers who's informational worlds interact with one another in order to combine into grander informational worlds. In this way, the reason that 2 people can both measure a tree as being the same height is because those 2 people have informational worlds that are dependent on another and therefore have their worlds combined into one “grander” informational world. Within this “grander” informational world, the tree must be of a height that is agreed upon by both of them since that height is discrete information that must fit cohesively in the grander informational world that includes both observers. Therefore, when 2 observers interact with one another they essentially “combine” their informational worlds since now each of their worlds information becomes dependent on the information of the other world.

Quantum Entanglement

Such a phenomenon can be seen in quantum entanglement where multiple quantum particles can have their informational properties be dependent on one another. For example, if a particle with a 0 spin angular momentum is separated into two particles, then if one particle is measured as “spin down” the other particle must then be known to be “spin up” no matter how much distance is between the 2 particles or when the first is measured. Note that this is not simply because both particles were each always “spin up” or “spin down” and only had their states revealed upon measurement. Rather it could be said that both particles were wave-like and essentially existed as having angular momentums in a superposition of both spin up and spin down angular momentum. However, when one was measured as “spin up” the second one then had to be “spin down” no matter the distance from the first. This phenomenon was proven by a series of experiments by John Stewart Bell that showed that such a correlation between the particles spin states could not be explained by them having discrete states all along. These series of experiments resulted in what has come to be known as “Bell’s Inequality”. (Though note that Bell’s inequality does assume “statistical independence” so any super-determinist view would still essentially render both particles as always having any states they eventually take on). Perhaps, this phenomenon can be explained simply because if one is particle is measured as “spin up” or +1 and the totality of both particles angular momentum was known to be 0, then the other particle then needs to have an angular momentum of -1 in order to fit into the informational world of the measurer and maintain causality. This shows that the reason that particles don’t take on “definitive properties” prior to measurement is because they don’t fundamentally exist in any “dimensional informational world” until they are measured. However, once they are measured the particles must take on dimensional informational existences inside the subjective worlds of observers and therefore must have information that fits in with the rest of the observers subjective world. In the case of the split 0 spin particle, the 0 spin particle always had to be split into particles with opposite spins in order for them to add up to 0 and make sense. Therefore when the first spin was measured as +1 the second had to be known to be -1 simply because it needed to fit into the informational cohesiveness of the subjective world. Furthermore, both particles essentially have informational that is “correlated with other another’s information” simply because they both exist within a grander context of an observer’s subjective world.

Since “observers” themselves are also essentially just physical systems they also can have “information” that is correlated with one another’s information and therefore be informationally “entangled”. For example, if one observers sees another observer then they can make judgments about that observer and gather information about that observer. In that way, the observers existing information now must fit in “cohesively” with the observations information inside the shared informational world that now includes both observers. It is this property of having shared information that is dependent on one another that allows observers to “agree” on measurements that seem objective when in reality they are only subjective and only seem to be objective since both observers exist in the the same “informational world”. Therefore, when thousands of scientists conduct experiments that agree on the “mass of an electron” they are essentially just all in the same “subjective informational world” that the measured mass of the electron must be consistent within.

Back to Zeno's Arrow

This understanding of how subjective informational worlds can be used to explain measurement can be applied to shed light on what's actually happening in Zeno's Arrow. Remember that in Zeno's arrow there is an infinite number of static "0 sized" moments that eventually make up a finite sized journey. However, the "paradox" that Zeno's Arrow demonstrates is how any culmination of 0 action moments could result in an actioned journey. The answer can be seen by thinking of Zeno's Arrow as an interaction between the observer who watches the arrow and the arrow. Each 0 action moment of the arrow's journey itself exists with no action because the observer's subjective "informational world" is required to provide the 0 action moments of the arrow's journey with a dimensional existence of time that allows for the arrow to actually "move". Once these 0 movement moments are placed within the subjective world or "context" of the observer, they can together manifest themselves as having a "temporally dimensional" existence that allows them to exist as a "line" of movement rather than just static points.

From here, it can be seen how such a "line" of movement can exist within the subjective world of an observer, when in reality the journey still objectively consists of an infinite amount of 0 action moments.

Summary

Objectively, there is only infinite and 0. This is simply because without speaking subjectively, all that can exist is 1 whole thing and its most indivisible potential components. The way in which these objective 0s constitute finite subjective entities involves the process of measurement. Measurement is therefore the process of how such objective indivisible information-less entities become "subjectified" with informational properties in the "informational worlds" of measurers.

Therefore, while objectively there are only infinity and "0", subjectively each individual informational world the 0s are placed in when measured allows them to take on a higher dimensional existence that renders them as entities that seem to make up more than the sum of their parts. In this way something is essentially just a contextualized amalgamation of infinite nothings existing in the informational world of an observer.

The glaringly obvious unexplained component here is the nature of "measurers" and what allows them to formulate their own "subjective informational worlds" in the first place. The next article will expand on the nature of observers and also explain why causality is necessary in constructing informationally cohesive worlds.